

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN AIZAWL CITY IN RELATION TO THEIR CLASS/STANDARD AND TYPE OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT

Zoramsanga¹, Dr. Vanlaltanpuii²,
Eunice V.L Fanai³ and Lallianzuali Fanai⁴

¹Research Scholar, IASE, Aizawl, Mizoram. E-mail: zoa.chongthu1@gmail.com
²Associate Professor, IASE, Aizawl, Mizoram. E-mail: vltanpuiihrahsel@gmail.com
³Research Scholar, IASE, Aizawl, Mizoram. E-mail: Eunice.Fanai@gmail.com
⁴Professor, IASE, Aizawl Mizoram. E-mail: dr.zuali@gmail.com

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Abstract

For the Present study, the researchers looked into the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City; and for the purpose of testing, the Class/Standard of the students i.e., Class-ix and Class-x were taken as Independent Variables including the Type of School Management which was broadly divided into two categories namely Government Managed Schools and Privately Managed Schools were selected. The researchers formulated the Null Hypotheses and 't'-test was applied to test the Null Hypotheses. The findings of the investigation noted no significant difference on the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to both the Independent Variables – Class/Standard that they are studying, and the type of School Management (Government Managed and Privately Managed) that they are attending. The result received implies that the level of Academic Achievement Motivation does not depend on Class/Standard and type of School Management that the Secondary School Students in Aizawl City are enrolled in.

Keywords: Academic Achievement Motivation, Class/Standard, Type of School Management, Secondary School Students.

INTRODUCTION

Academic Achievement Motivation is one of the driving forces that compels a student to succeed in their academic endeavors. Motivation may be regarded as the drive and enthusiasm that makes a person wants to perform a task; therefore, Academic Achievement Motivation may be regarded as the drive that compels a person to perform tasks that would eventually lead to academic success.

Therefore, motivation is the driving force behind every action and it maintains a goal-directed behavior in the individuals. Motivation can be divided into two broad categories – Intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is referred to as the kind of motivation that comes from within a person. For example, for the love of teaching, one might be motivated to teach and might not be due to monetary gains.

Extrinsic motivation is that motivation that comes externally from our environment; for example, an elementary student may be motivated to score good marks if a reward is promised.

Extrinsic motivation may also act as a positive reinforcer. What reinforcement actually do to a person is that it motivates that person to perform the same act that was just reinforced. With every reinforcement given, the probability that the reinforced behavior will occur again is increased.

Academic motivation or academic achievement motivation has a significant correlation with academic achievement of the students (Amrai et al., 2011). The higher the academic motivation, the higher the academic achievement.

Therefore, it may also be understood that the level of academic motivation that a student has can make or break the level of academic achievement that he/she acquires. Motivation is regarded as an important factor in the teaching-learning line of work. It is due to this that teachers need to be trained to be able to motivate their classes or students among many other things.

Academic Achievement Motivation may also be an important factor in determining future jobs; the kind of job that a person has determines his/her socio-economic status and eventually the family he/she belongs to. Professional jobs with a high paying salary are only achievable if one meets the minimum educational qualification criteria needed.

Some professional jobs require extensive amount of study and the duration of the study also takes much longer than that of regular courses of study. Hence, academic achievement motivation is the guiding force to sustain a certain level of academic achievement. Therefore, the importance of academic achievement motivation should not be underestimated.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Soni (2013) in his research article “A Study of the Relationship between Academic Achievement Motivation and Home Environment among Standard 10th Pupils” noted a positive relationship between academic achievement motivation and home environment.

The finding of the study implied that home environment is one of the determinants of academic achievement motivation and this could be because a household with academically favorable home environment is likely to enhance the child’s motivation to achieve academic success. The sample of the study consisted of 155 students of 10th Standard from Palanpur Taluka.

Phukan (January, 2015) in the article “Academic Achievement Motivation of Students Studying in the Secondary Schools of the Dibrugarh District” noted a significant difference in the level of academic achievement motivation of male students from a government managed school and male students from private managed schools. The male students from government schools have a higher level of Academic Achievement Motivation as compared to their male counterpart studying in private schools.

The study also noted a significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of female students from government schools and private schools; the observed difference is in favor of female students from private schools.

Perween (2020) conducted an investigation on “A Comparative Study of Academic Achievement Motivation of High School Students” and the study noted a significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Government High School Students and Private High School Students. The high school students from private institutions have a higher level of academic achievement motivation than those from government schools.

Sheergugri et al. (February, 2021) in their research article, “A Comparative Study of Academic Achievement of Government and Private Secondary School Students in Gwalior City of M.P.”, they noted a significant difference between the Academic Achievement Motivation of secondary school students from government and private schools. The said significant is in favor of those students from privately managed schools.

Zoramsanga et al. (2023) in their investigation titled “A Study of The Academic Achievement Motivation of Higher Secondary School Students of Aizawl City in Relation to Their Gender, Class/Grade and Mother’s Occupation” took a sample of 150 Higher Secondary School Students in Aizawl City; 75 students each from both government and private schools were taken. The study noted a significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation; Class-xi students have a higher level of Academic Achievement Motivation as compared to Class-xii students.

Saini and Gautam (July, 2024) conducted a study titled “Academic Achievement Motivation: A Comparative Study of Government and Private Secondary School Students during Pandemic Online Classes”, the study constituted a sample size of 200 Secondary School Students where 100 are taken from Government Schools (50 girls + 50 Boys) and another 100 are taken from Private Schools (50 girls + 50 boys).

Their study noted a significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary Students during the pandemic online classes. The students from private schools have a higher level of Academic Achievement Motivation during the pandemic online classes.

Objectives of the Study

For the present study, the researchers have given the following research objectives:

1. To find out the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to their Class/Standard (Class-IX and Class-X level) in school.
2. To investigate the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to the Type of School Management (Government VS Private).

Null Hypotheses

For the purpose of testing, the investigators have formulated the following Null Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Class-IX and Class-X Secondary School Students in Aizawl City.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City with regards to the Type of School Management.

Design, Methodology and Procedure

Quantitative Survey method of research and descriptive analysis were employed for the present study. After the data was collected, the raw scores of the respondents were calculated.

The Mean and Standard Deviation were determined and the ‘t’-test of statistical significance was applied to test the Null Hypotheses and conclusion was drawn according to the findings.

Population and Sample

The population of the study consisted of class-ix and class-x students in Aizawl City. A total of 150 students – 75 from Government Schools and 75 from Private Schools, were the sample taken for the present study. Sampling was done via the Stratified Random Sampling technique.

Tool

The investigators administered the “Academic Achievement Motivation Test” (AAMT) developed by T.R. Sharma. The tool contains a total of 38 items and was designed to be used on school going children of age 14yrs and above.

FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Findings and interpretation on the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to their Class/Standard.

Table 1: Significant of Difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation among Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to their Class/Standard.

Class/Standard	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	t'-Value	Level of Significance
IX	72	21.9	3.32	0.1	Not Significant
X	78	21.97	4.87		

Fig 1: Graphical Representation of the Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of the Academic Achievement Motivation test of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to their Class/Standard in School

Perusal of the data vide **table-1** shows that there is no significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students of Aizawl city in relation to their class/standard (class ix and class x).

The calculated 't' value is 0.1. The 't' value required to be significant at .05 and .01 levels are 1.98 and 2.61 respectively. Since the calculated 't' value i.e .01 is smaller than the table value of 't' even at the .05 level, the Null Hypothesis is accepted.

2. Findings and interpretation on the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to the Type of School Management.

Table 2: Significant Difference between the Mean Scores of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to the Type of School Management

Type of School Management	N	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	't'- Value	Level of Significance
Government Schools	75	21.76	4.57	0.53	Not Significant
Private Schools	75	21.12	3.83		

Fig 2: Graphical Representation of the Mean Scores and Standard Deviation obtained by Secondary School Students in Aizawl City in relation to the Type of School Management

As seen on Table-2, the calculated 't' value is 0.53. The 't' value that is required to be significant at .05 level and .01 level are 1.98 and 2.61 respectively. Since the calculated 't' value is still smaller than the table value of 't' at the .05 level, the Null Hypothesis cannot be rejected because no significant difference was noted on the level of Academic Achievement Motivation among High School students in Aizawl city in relation to the type of school management (Government VS Private) that they are attending. Hence, the Null Hypothesis is accepted in this case.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study with regards to the class/grade/standard of the students revealed that the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students of Aizawl city is not influenced by the class/standard/grade that the students are currently in. The findings made in the present study could be due to the

fact that, irrespective of whether the students are in class-ix or class-x, the students are treated alike and are both under pressure to perform in the matriculation examination. This could be the reason why both groups have the same level of motivation for academic achievement, though both groups are at the same level it is not without a difference; however, the difference is too narrow to be statistically significant.

The finding made in the present study, in relation to type of school management, is not consistent with the findings made by Phukan (January, 2015) where she noted a statistically significant difference between male students from government schools and male students from private schools; the Academic Achievement Motivation of male students from government schools is higher. The investigator also noted another significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of female students from government schools and female students from private schools. The female students from the private managed schools have a higher level of Academic Achievement Motivation. Sheergugri et al. (February, 2021) also noted a significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation between students from government schools and students from private schools where students from private schools harbor a higher level of Academic Achievement Motivation.

Saini and Gautam (July, 2024) also noted that there is a significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School students from government schools and private schools during the pandemic online classes; the students from private schools have a higher level of Academic Achievement Motivation during the pandemic online classes. Likewise, Perween (2020) also noted the same significant difference in favor of those students from a private high school. However, the present study finds contradicting result from previous studies. The study noted no significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students of Aizawl city on the basis of the type of school management that the students are attending. The fact that high school students have to face the prestigious matriculation exam could be the driving force as to why there is no difference. Both group of students have to go through the same matriculation examination, whether government or private, without any distinction and the course content are the same in both types of school management. Therefore, this might be the potential reason as to why no difference was detected when testing the hypothesis.

CONCLUSION

As per the findings made by the investigators, The Null Hypothesis “There is no significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Class-IX and Class-X Secondary School Students in Aizawl City” is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that, the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City does not get effected by the standard/class that the students are studying in.

Also, the Null Hypothesis stating that “There is no significant difference in the level of Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City with regards to the Type of School Management” is also accepted. The finding implies that the Academic Achievement Motivation of Secondary School Students in Aizawl City is not affected by whether the school is under the Government Management or Private Management.

Recommendations for Further Studies

1. To study the level of academic achievement motivation of post-graduate students and under-graduate students of Aizawl City.
2. To study the effect of parental occupations on the level of academic achievement motivation of their children.
3. To conduct a correlational study on academic achievement motivation and academic aptitude

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